

Conceptual Design for the Advancement of Mechanical Counterpressure Spacesuits

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With expected increased demand for extravehicular activity in future exploration missions, the superficially simple nature of mechanical counterpressure (MCP) spacesuits holds significant appeal while promising numerous advantages. While traditional gas-pressurized suits have proven reliable for many decades, MCP's skin-tight garments have the potential to offer significant improvements in mobility, dexterity, level of exertion and safety. Numerous unsolved design challenges exist which have prevented the adoption of this technology. This paper discusses work undertaken towards engineering solutions for some of these issues, prioritizing the demonstration of viability in experimental conditions. By considering mechanical components rather than material properties, this project investigates a way to achieve the generation of the large tensions required for a functional MCP suit. The concepts are examined in the context of comfort and donning speed for such a spacesuit. Garment adjustability is also considered to address concerns surrounding changes to body shape during long-duration missions, as well as providing better performance and reduced production costs.

Nomenclature

<i>xEMU</i>	=	Exploration Extravehicular Mobility Unit
<i>EPG</i>	=	Environmental Protection Garment
<i>EVA</i>	=	Extravehicular Activity
<i>GP</i>	=	Gas Pressure
<i>ISS</i>	=	International Space Station
<i>MCP</i>	=	Mechanical Counterpressure
<i>NASA</i>	=	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
<i>OD</i>	=	Outer Diameter
<i>ROM</i>	=	Range of Motion
<i>SMA</i>	=	Shape Memory Alloy
P_1	=	Pressure
P_2	=	Counterpressure
r	=	Radius

I. Introduction

Exploration is part of human nature. Due to the growing demands of extravehicular activity (EVA) planned for future missions, the development of a redesigned advanced spacesuit is a necessity. Current designs have relied on compression through gas pressure (GP) within a sealed garment to protect astronauts. Whilst this approach has proven reliable and has been consistently used for many decades, it can limit astronauts' capability to perform EVA tasks effectively. Several major disadvantages of the present generation of GP suits include limited dexterity and mobility due to the high level of pressurization that they require¹, and excessive weight. Additionally, material stiffness and lack of appropriate sizing result in elevated levels of injuries during EVA and training².

Instead, Mechanical Counterpressure (MCP) spacesuits use the tension of a skin-tight garment to apply pressure directly on the surface body. By removing the need for GP suits, this disruptive technology allows for significant

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improvements in range of motion (ROM), comfort, compactness, energy exertion, and safety^{3,4,5}. This concept has been investigated as an alternative to GP suits for over 50 years from suits inspired by traditional high altitude partial pressure suits to the implementation of novel smart materials. However, successfully maintaining the necessary level of pressure uniformly distributed around the body by a tightly wrapped fabric is a complex problem, one that has seen slow progression⁶. The primary non-thermal challenges associated with MCP suits that have resulted in a declined interest over the years include tensioning, pressure generation, pressure uniformity, and donning.

This paper presents an investigation of an engineering solution to improve ROM, compactness, and energy exertion of the system whilst drastically reducing the production cost. The objective is to demonstrate the viability of this MCP technology through practical implementation and experimental testing. This study is specifically focused on the forearm region of the suit due to its simplicity in modeling and does not address the complexities of glove attachments and elbow interfaces. The project employs a mechanical component-based approach to achieve the necessary tensions for a functional MCP suit, emphasizing the advantages of tension generation over material properties. Importantly, this approach does not require the use of advanced materials or specialized equipment, which may facilitate further innovations in MCP design.

II. Existing Techniques

There are currently several different architectures that exist for pressure garments, including GP suits, MCP suits and several concepts for GP-MCP hybrids. Despite research into these differing concepts, the overall architecture of spacesuits has only undergone minor changes, with the majority still relying on internal air pressure.

A. High Altitude Pressure Suits

In the early 20th Century, advancements in aircraft technology enabled pilots to reach higher altitudes, resulting in the need for protective wear. The discovery that the human body has a physiological limit for sustaining exposure to these altitudes without loss of consciousness sparked a new area of research in the development of pressure suits. They were designed to maintain a positive pressure environment around the user's body, thereby preventing hypoxia and decompression sickness. The first pressure suit concepts consisted of simple airtight garments, typically rubber, nylon, or *Gore-Tex*, connected to an air supply through a hose and an air bladder commonly made of neoprene.

After multiple suits were developed, it became apparent that fully pressurized suits limited the mobility of the pilots to the extent that made them unsuitable for military purposes. This resulted in a shift towards partial pressure suits that consisted of tight-fitting garments with capstan tubes that, once inflated, could stretch the garment fabric, and exert pressure^{7,8}. The suits often came in multiple sizes where fine adjustments could be made by tightening laces throughout, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1- MC-3A Partial Pressure Suit. *Front and back view with the MA-2 Helmet. The suit also includes the capstan system and a full-torso bladder around the vital organs. Image from Ref. 8.*

The cylindrical capstan tube is made of a flexible silicone material that can withstand sufficient deviatoric stresses without rupturing. The tube is typically wrapped within a garment and connected to the suit via crossing tapes located at the base. In some cases, adhesive or heat-sealing techniques are also used to attach the tube to the fabric. Once inflated, the hoop stress creates a frictional force between the tube and the skin, preventing slipping or moving. Fixed into this stationary position, the crossing tapes act as pneumatic levels, applying a uniform pressure onto the pilot's body⁸.

Although they require some specialized components and precise manufacturing techniques, this concept, in comparison to other aviation suits, is not costly. Due to the narrow margin of optimum pressure, the suits are custom made to ensure they are tight enough to provide the necessary tension and support, but not to restrict movement or cause serious discomfort. This involves taking accurate measurements to tailor the suit to their wearer's specific dimensions. Modern partial pressure suits are designed to accommodate a range of body types and sizes, reducing the need for extensive customization in many cases. It is also important to note that repairs and maintenance of these suits are not complicated as most of the components can be detached and replaced as needed.

The location of the pressurized gas tank varies depending on the design of the partial pressure suit. In some cases, it is integrated into the garment and worn on the pilot's back, while in others, it is carried separately as an external component. However, due to several factors including limitations in the design of the suit, the pressure rating of the gas tank, and the tolerance of the wearer to the sustained pressure, the partial pressure suit can only be activated for short durations primarily in low-pressure environments. These are typically during emergencies in which the cabin pressure has rapidly decreased.

B. Traditional Spacesuits

The fundamental design of the spacesuit has remained unchanged since the early 1960s and still uses pressurized garments to maintain a breathable atmosphere around the astronaut⁹. Whilst the concept has remained the same, improvements have been made for materials, mobility, and life support systems. The arm section of the EMU suits currently worn on the International Space Station (ISS) consist of 14 layers, each serving a specific purpose. The innermost layers of the suit are composed of the Liquid Cooling and Ventilation Garment, which helps regulate a comfortable body temperature by circulating water around the body. The bladder layer comes next, followed by the restraint pressure garment, which is constructed from a plain weave polyester fabric, and a neoprene ripstop liner. The Thermal Micrometeoroid Garment covers the outside surface and provides thermal insulation and protection from micrometeoroid impacts. It also serves as routing and coverage of the O₂ line and actuator cables¹⁰.

The GP design has several limitations, including limited ROM and large resistive joint torques resulting in discomfort, increased injury risk¹¹, and high levels of exertion during movement^{12,13}. To address these limitations, several prototype suits have been developed, including the exploration extravehicular mobility unit (xEMU), which is currently under development to replace the EMUs¹⁴. The xEMU is a combination of the most effective architectural features from previous GP suit prototypes¹⁵.

C. Current MCP Spacesuits

1. Development

MCP technology has been explored since the 1960s, but practical applications have been limited due to the technical challenges involved¹⁶. Under the commission of the United States Air Force, the initial development of a full MCP suit aimed to enhance both mobility and flexibility and surpass limitations of the fully pressurized suits. The proposed design featured a closed-cell foam core layered between two sheets of fabric. This approach allowed the suit to leverage the mechanics of the foam's elasticity, enabling it to expand in response to the reduced atmospheric pressure and create a compressive force that conformed to the wearer's body shape. However, after rigorous testing, the suit failed to achieve the required level of mobility and reduction in weight⁹. The next major milestone was the Space Activity Suit completed by Paul Webb and James Annis in 1971 which remains the only fully evaluated MCP

Figure 2- EMU arm schematic. 14 layers. Image from Ref. 10.

suit to date¹⁷. Whilst showing great promise and paving the way for future innovation, the suit's lack of flexibility and failure to provide uniform compression were significant limitations. A more thorough history of the Space Activity Suit was recently compiled by MacFarland, Ross and Sanders¹³.

Recently, advancements in smart materials such as biomechanical, shape memory alloys (SMA) or nanomaterials, have been considered for MCP application. This alternative concept allows the suit to actively maintain constant tension through large increases as well as assisting with donning/doffing¹⁸.

2. Elements

The concept of using a tightly wrapped elastic garment for compression, such as the *Bio-Suit* proposal, is currently considered the most viable option for MCP suits¹⁹. The fabric elements must perform well in various states: when tension is applied, in a resting state, and during physical movement. This elastic, non-linear material would require a very large initial extension to apply constant pressure for these range of states²⁰. The majority of elastic materials exhibit stiffnesses levels that are too low.

Load-bearing fabrics are commonly used to allow for control over the stiffness of the fabric in different directions³. This is achieved by altering the fibers within the weave to provide the necessary properties. Whilst elastic garments are often used and offer many desirable properties for an MCP suit, there are also several potential negatives to consider. The extreme temperature variations in space environments can cause elastomers to degrade and lose their elastic properties, compromising the performance of the suit. High levels of radiation can cause damage over time by inducing chain scission and breaking the chemical bonds within the material's polymer chain. This degradation ultimately leads to brittle failure²¹. This exposure can also result in crosslinking, which makes the elastomer stiffer and thus reduces flexibility when wearing the suit²². Outgassing is another concern when using certain elastomers in a space environment. When exposed to low pressure, the material can release small amounts of gas, such as water vapor or other volatile compounds²³. This accumulation can result in an increase in pressure, causing the suit to expand or even rupture. This might cause issues if the MCP layer was integrated into a hybrid system.

The slip layer is a crucial element that serves as a low friction surface between the body of the wearer and the main pressure-generation layers of the suit. The outer layers of the suit are able to move independently from the inner, preventing the development of shear forces, friction, and chaffing²⁴. This in turn affects the tension loss and variation in MCP applied onto the body²⁵. It also houses the monitoring equipment and sensors as well as providing some limited padding to help distribute pressure evenly across the skin's surface, and thus reducing the risk of injury caused by localized high-pressure points.

3. Feasibility

The underlying MCP technologies, design, and material selection have not yet demonstrated the ability to consistently provide the required uniform pressure needed for space exploration²⁶. The fundamental challenge of existing approaches is to develop a material structure that can apply this uniform pressure whilst maintaining flexibility and durability. The placement of the tensioning system is key in controlling the maximum attainable counterpressure. Various MCP suit concepts have considered active element weaved throughout the fabric, localized in one region, or placed externally onto the suit^{3,15,27}. The system's ability to automatically regulate the pressure applied in response to temperature, movement, and external conditions through the use of sensors and actuators is also an important consideration. Another consideration is the sizing sensitivity of the suit and establishing the narrow margin needed for sufficient pressure^{9,28}.

Due to the lack of research in this field, the primary viability of MCP through human subject testing has been conducted on a glove²⁹. The Honeywell/NASA EVA prototype glove underwent rigorous testing, where the time required to complete a range of tasks was compared with that of a GP pressurized glove. The results demonstrated that the MCP design was up to four times faster, highlighting the potential benefits. The tests also provided validity of the interface between GP garments and MCP systems. Despite significant efforts, non-uniform pressure distribution continues to be observed, particularly in flat and concave regions^{30,31}.

III. Description of Conceptual Spacesuit

A. Preliminary Considerations

The primary objective of this project is to construct a working prototype of the suit that can apply the necessary pressure without the need for constant power application. A design was taken to reduce the suit's complexity by utilizing mechanical systems to generate tension rather than relying on smart materials that can be prone to degradation, disassembly, power failure and malfunction. The use of an electrically powered suit poses several concerns including the reliability, durability, and requisite power density for tension generation. Radiation, extreme temperatures, and vacuum conditions can significantly impact the performance and longevity of electronic systems as

well as the material properties used within the fabric, potentially compromising the functionality of the suit itself. The complexity of the control system adds another layer of potentially harmful malfunction.

In addition to the primary objective, several capacity requirements were identified as critical for the suit's use in a space environment. These requirements include: the ability to apply pressure effectively and safely, maintain a full range of motion and dexterity, minimize bulk, facilitate maintenance and repair, and allow for easy donning/doffing and sizing adjustments. The application of pressure is crucial to the functioning of the MCP suit, and as such, significant attention was given to its design as well as ensuring the suit provides adequate protection to the user. The suit was designed to minimize bulk and ensure it does not impede the wearer's movement. The MCP suit has been designed with accessible maintenance and repair in mind to ensure it can be worn throughout the mission when changes in body shape are likely to occur. As mentioned previously, this is a research concept focusing on the forearm section and does not include areas around the main joints (e.g. elbow or wrist).

In the proposed suit design, the specific details of how the developed section integrates with the remainder of the suit have not been thoroughly addressed. It can be inferred that the development section is part of a GP-MCP hybrid, whereby the limbs incorporate this novel MCP technology, and the body utilizes a design appropriate for breathing considerations¹. The seamless integration of various body regions to achieve uniform pressure distribution has not been considered as it is an outstanding issue meriting research of its own.

B. General Overview

This MCP suit concept draws inspiration from early partial pressure suits, which rely on the implementation of a single capstan tube located on the upper surface of the forearm. As illustrated in Figure 3, the design features a simple yet efficient system that can be categorized into three fundamental components: pressure application, support structures, and fabrics.

The pressure application is comprised of a tensioning system and locking mechanism. Thin fiber cables are looped around the forearm to apply compression onto the body once the capstan tube is inflated. The locking mechanism consists of a smooth zipper located below the capstan tube which, for preliminary testing, is closed by pulling an elastic cable through the gap. Once securely closed, the pressure can be released from the capstan tube. There are two primary support structures. The capstan spacer serves to maintain a uniform gap between the capstan tube and the forearm, facilitating easier zipper closure. The cable housing guides the individual Vectran woven cables to maintain equidistance. Within this conceptual design, three primary fabrics that have been considered including the zipper fabric, the outer garment, and the comfort layer.

Other features outside this segment of the forearm have not been considered for this design. It is assumed that the gas tank can be located within the exploration habitat or within a portable vessel that can be transported to other areas as a backup.

Figure 3- MCP forearm section. Rendered image showing all primary components.

C. Pressure Application

1. Tensioning System

The MCP suit's forearm section is comprised of hundreds of thin, equidistant cables that loop around the limb, which, upon capstan tube inflation, provide compressive force onto the body. The looped configuration of each cable ensures that the tension is evenly distributed throughout. Once the zipper is closed, the pressure generated by the inflated capstan is maintained, ensuring the compression remains consistent throughout the limb. As illustrated in Figure 3, the radius of the suit prior to capstan pressurization is marginally larger, allowing the forearm to slide into position with greater ease. Additionally, a fabric bridge is added on the underside of the zipper to maintain the proximity and orientation of the two zipper heads.

Figure 4- Pressure Application Schematic. A. Showing the system in a relaxed state with an open zipper. B. Showing the tensioned state with the capstan fully inflated and the zipper closed. P_1 is the internal pressure of the capstan tube, P_2 is the pressure exerted onto the forearm. Grey sections on forearm circumference are cable housing.

2. Locking Mechanism

This design incorporates an open channel located above the zipper, which is supported by a capstan spacer to restrict downwards capstan tube expansion. The capstan spacer, akin to a conventional cufflink, pinches the fabric at the base to ensure complete cable enclosure around the tube. The open channel prevents zipper interference, whilst elastic cables secured on both sides of the zipper head enable bidirectional movement. Once the capstan tube attains the minimum pressure threshold, the zipper ends come into sufficient proximity for closure. This process involves simply pulling the string upwards for suit closure and downwards for suit removal. This user-friendly approach requires no technical expertise and can be executed using the user's opposite hand. Additionally, an extra locking mechanism in the form of a Velcro tab can be included to secure the zipper head in place and prevent any unintended movement.

D. Component Design and Material Selection

1. Cable-

The cables are made of Vectran. Its exceptional resistance to stretching or creep under applied loads, combined with its high tensile strength, make it the optimal synthetic fiber for this application. Furthermore, Vectran exhibits remarkable thermal stability and resistance to abrasion, providing unparalleled durability and longevity to the entire system. Given that the cables are the most vulnerable component, the use of Vectran ensures the system remains robust even in the most demanding conditions.

2. Capstan Tube and Tube Liner

The choice of silicone rubber as the capstan material was selected due to the materials flexibility, high-temperature resistance, and high coefficient of friction³². Its excellent elasticity and resilience also allow it to withstand multiple loading cycles without compromising its mechanical properties. This MCP suit differs from other constant power systems in that pressure is momentarily applied to the capstan tube until the system is locked. In partial pressure suits, the dimensions of the capstan tube, such as thickness and diameter, are critical in ensuring efficient and uniform function. The focus of this design is to generate sufficient pressure to exceed the threshold mark and successfully close the zipper.

The tube liner acts as a sleeve that surrounds the capstan tube. The inclusion of a low-friction material on the external surface of the liner facilitates the removal of the capstan tube from the outer garment, enabling efficient maintenance of the system.

3. Zipper

After rigorous testing of different zippers, a flat waterproof zipper was proven to perform the best under high tension and far exceeded the maximum tension required before failure. Several parameters were considered during testing, including tooth size, tooth material, zipper fabric thickness, and glide ability.

The zipper is made of a nylon base and a polyurethane film lamination on its reverse side. Although the addition of the film marginally reduces the flexibility of the zipper, its flat upper surface allows for greater freedom of movement for the slider. Once testing for environmental conditions is complete, other locking mechanisms will also be explored and tested as an alternative to the zipper.

A.

B.

Figure 5- Experimental Setup. A. Prepared zipper samples for testing the effect of different materials and configurations. B. Tensile tests performed until failure on the Instron-8801 to compare.

4. Comfort and Slip Layer

The comfort layer will be made of a compressive, form-fitting, material which adds sufficient padding to the forearm. The polyethylene slip layer is worn around the comfort layer. This tailored garment can assist with automatic tensioning and reduce donning time by providing a low-friction surface between the suit and the wearers' skin, minimizing the force required to put on the suit. During the tensioning process, the slip layer will allow the MCP suit to adjust its shape and tension without causing excessive friction on the skin.

5. Cable Housing

To ensure a secure attachment between the zipper fabric and the outer garment, five points of stitching are employed around the circumference. These stitches are positioned in line with the cable housing, which provides a stable anchor point for the system's tension when the zipper is closed (See cable housing in Figure 4). The cable

housing is designed with a series of arched extruded cuts along the base, which enables the cables to move freely below while maintaining an equidistant distance from one another as they warp around the forearm.

There are two sets of holes running along the top face of the housing in which the stitching will pass through, as shown in the schematic below. A double-needle lockstitch will be used to ensure that it remains secure during repeated use. High strength Vectran threads have been selected for all aspects of stitching within the spacesuit due to their exceptional strength and low elongation.

Figure 6- Cable Housing with stitching. Front and side view with two-thread stitching through the cable housing (grey), outer garment (blue) and zipper fabric (red). The stitching fiber is highlighted in yellow for clarity.

E. Sizing Adjustments

In order to accommodate the changing dimensions of astronauts during space missions, the zipper fabric has been developed with an adjustable length feature on one of its sides. The zipper fabric is looped around the main frame and securely stitched into position with the overlay fabric on either side to ensure stability. Reinforcement has been integrated within the zipper fabric to prevent tearing under high tension or stitching failure. Two series of closely spaced zigzag stitches are utilized to provide durability and flexibility, maintaining a comfortable fit for the user. This technique has been employed to allow for easy removal and resewing. It is assumed that any potential changes to the astronaut's body throughout the course of the mission would fall within an acceptable range, such that adjustments to the size of the capstan tube or incorporation of length mechanisms on both ends of the zipper would not be necessary.

Dynamic dimension alteration is a critical feature for ensuring that the MCP suit maintains optimal functionality. The suit's design enables manual sizing adjustments if necessary, providing an additional layer of adaptability. The modular architecture of each individual component within the spacesuit enables separate replacement of parts, minimizing the disruption of the overall system.

Figure 7- Sizing Adjustability Mechanism. The stitching fiber is highlighted in yellow for clarity.

IV. System Development

A. Assembly Development

The current conceptual design is still undergoing development and further manufacturing. Figure 8 shows the latest version of the prototype, which includes all the primary components. However, to evaluate the capstan's required pressure to achieve optimal tension in the cables, additional components are needed.

The cable housing plays a crucial role in guiding the Vectran and preventing any entanglement. It is important to maintain a uniform distance between all the cables to prevent the restriction of movement and areas of exposed skin. Within this project, the gap distance between each of the cable housing guides is 0.5mm. It is assumed that this is sufficiently small to avoid any medical issues including extrusion/swelling^{33,34}. To counteract this, a possible alternative is to incorporate weaving techniques to keep the cables aligned with the fabric, promoting uniformity. Further research would be necessary to determine the ideal weaving method to prevent restriction of movement with capstan pressurization.

In order to conduct the core testing for pressure generation of the MCP suit prototype, one end of the tube will be clamped while the other is connected to a manual or electric pump equipped with a pressure gauge for continuous monitoring and regulation. To ensure unrestricted cable movement and simplicity, this will be carried out without the zipper included in the system. Instead, a circular cloth of the desired diameter will act as a sleeve. An inflatable tube will be placed in the limb region of the prototype and pressurized until an equilibrium point is reached, in which the cables remain stationary. The aforementioned process will be repeated until the counterpressure of the limb region reaches 29.6kPa³⁵. Once an approximate estimate for the required internal pressure of the capstan is obtained (specific to material selection and diameter), the experiment will be repeated using pressure sensors over a rigid cylindrical structure to ensure greater precision and accuracy.

Figure 8- Latest experimental prototype. 1.2mm Vectran cables, 14mm OD rubber latex tube, and waterproof 3mm teeth.

Figure 9- Experimental Setup. Clamped capstan tube and inflated forearm section tube.

B. Limitations

The implementation of the zipper as a locking mechanism has several challenging aspects, including the risk of becoming jammed or stuck during donning/doffing in an emergency. The main reasons why this occurs is misalignment of the teeth, debris caught in the zipper track, or damage to the body of the slider itself. To prevent these issues, regular maintenance and cleaning of the zipper and surrounding area is important. Lubricating the zipper with silicone or wax can also prevent sticking but can sometimes be prone to attracting dust particles.

Achieving an optimal ROM is critical in the development of a successful MCP suit. To ensure that the capstan spacer does not restrict the user's movement during inflation or EVA, it is essential to conduct further research on the ergonomics, design, and size of the spacer. Although this becomes less of a concern once the zipper is closed and the pressure is released, there is still room for improvement in this area.

A major limitation of this project is the safety of the suit in the vacuum environment. While the primary focus of this project is on pressure application, locking mechanism, donning and doffing, and ROM, other aspects including safety, physiology and comfort concerns are deemed secondary due to the current testing facilities and financing available. Thermal analysis could also be conducted to help in understanding how the suit will behave in extreme temperatures.

C. Other Considerations

1. Comfort

Although this is a conceptual design in the early stages of development, a successful MCP spacesuit is dependent on not only achieving the required parameters but also considering the wearers comfort. Past research and testing have demonstrated that comfort issues can worsen drastically. While some previous MCP tests have been able to run for longer than their predetermined duration limit, there is little evidence to suggest that SMA MCP systems would be comfortable for a full EVA. This is due to issues included but not limited to pressure application, dynamic movement effects, uniformity, interface, and garment construction. The proposed design, which applies the main tensioning system externally onto the body, offers greater freedom in selecting an improved comfort layer compared to the woven-in smart material technology. However, further refinement of prototypes and extensive long-duration testing is necessary to fully understand the impact of MCP on wearer comfort and identify potential solutions to mitigate any discomfort, enabling extended operations of up to eight hours.

2. Environmental Protection

The design of the Spacesuit for future missions must take into account the environmental conditions, which necessitates the inclusion of environmental protection garments (EPGs) in the overall design. These cover garments provide essential protection from a range of hazards, including dust, micrometeorites, abrasions, radiation exposure, cuts, and thermal extremes³⁶.

In this proposed design, EPGs have not been included in the main system as further research would be required to determine the most effective materials and design configurations for the suit. It is assumed that the EPG would be worn as an outer layer and tailored to the specific requirements of the final design. A potential candidate for this application is carbon nanotube flexible fiber that can be embedded into the outer layer. It acts as electrode wires and pushes the dust off the material surface when activated with a multi-phase alternating current³⁷.

As the suit will be zipped closed within the base, an additional layer can be conveniently donned after depressurizing the capstan tubes to minimize the amount of dust that is able to penetrate through the system and interfere with the zipper mechanism.

V. Conclusions and Future Work

The ongoing project is directed towards the development of a highly functional and optimized MCP spacesuit, which necessitates further advancement to produce a compression system capable of achieving the desired pressure with uniformity across the system. The proposed conceptual suit features a new approach to tackling pressure generation by considering mechanical components rather than material properties. This approach results in a self-sustaining space suit design that would eliminate the need for bulky and heavy power sources, allowing for a significant reduction in overall weight and enabling longer EVAs. The potential for power-related malfunctions would be greatly reduced, thus improving the safety of space exploration. The modular architecture of the suit enables individual components to be removed and replaced when necessary, minimizing the disruption of the overall system.

As the project moves into its subsequent phase, it will entail rigorous testing and comprehensive data analysis to evaluate the functionality of the various components within the overarching system. Through this, there will be further insights into the potential constraints and limitations of the suit, enabling final optimization for the necessary refinements and enhancements to meet the standards of performance and reliability required for the next generation of space exploration. Dimension alternation is critical for the new generation of MCP suits. This work could be further assessed to evaluate the accuracy of the adjustable length feature and its ability to maintain optimal functionality after being resewn. Misalignment could result in pressure distributions throughout the forearm, as well as areas of stress concentrations that could result in fabric or attachment failure.

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